

Comparative Study of Assessment of Fetal Risk in Pregnancy Beyond 40 Weeks with That of Pregnancy between 37-40 Weeks

G. Chandrakala¹, Paidi Swarnalatha², Jyothirmayi Ponnada³, Amrutha Vippala⁴, Darapu Goutami⁵

¹MS, Associate Professor, Government Medical College/GGH/Srikakulam, AP

²MS, Assistant Professor, Government Medical College/GGH/Srikakulam, AP

³MS, Associate Professor, Government Medical College/GGH/Srikakulam, AP

⁴MS, Assistant Professor, Government Medical College/GGH/Srikakulam, AP

⁵MS, Assistant Professor, Government Medical College/GGH/Srikakulam, AP

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Darapu Goutami

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Perinatal outcome has been shown to be jeopardized by prolongation of pregnancy beyond 40 weeks with an increase in perinatal morbidity and mortality being ascribed to uteroplacental insufficiency and cord compression. Consequently, the question of whether a pregnancy that proceeds to more than 40 weeks should be considered a high-risk pregnancy remains a controversial issue.

Objectives: To assess the foetal outcome in pregnancies beyond 40 weeks and to compare with foetal outcome in pregnancies between 37-40 weeks.

Methods: A prospective case controls study of 100 cases of women who delivered beyond 40 weeks of gestation and 100 cases of women who delivered between 37-40 weeks respectively in Government General Hospital, Government Medical College, Srikakulam, AP, during June, 2023-June, 2024.

Result: The incidence of meconium, low Apgar score, foetal distress, NICU admission and caesarean section increases significantly beyond 40 weeks. Compared to 37-40 weeks.

Conclusion: Risk to both mother and infant increases as pregnancy progress beyond 40 weeks of gestation.

Keywords: Pregnancy between 37-40 weeks; Pregnancy beyond 40 weeks; Meconium; Foetal distress; Caesarean section.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The prolongation of pregnancy beyond 40 weeks occurs frequently that is 1 in every 10 pregnancies. Perinatal mortality and morbidity are increased in prolong pregnancy, perinatal mortality is two to three times in these prolonged gestation. Fetal mortality in pregnancies that exceed 42 weeks in length is almost doubled than that seen in patients who delivered between 37 to 41 weeks.

Aims and Objectives

1. To study the perinatal outcome in pregnancy beyond 40 weeks in terms of fetal distress meconium aspiration syndrome, Birth Asphyxia and HIE.
2. To study the time and mode of delivery in cases of pregnancy beyond 40 weeks.
3. Proper selection of cases for induction of labor and surgical intervention.
4. To study in incidence of operative and instrumental delivery in pregnancies beyond 40 weeks.

5. To study the incidence of Oligohydromnios in pregnancy beyond 40 weeks.
6. To compare the fetomaternal outcome in pregnancy beyond 40 weeks with that of pregnancies between 37-40 weeks.

Materials and Methods

A prospective study of 100 cases that crossed the expected date of delivery was conducted during the year June 2023-June 2024 in Government General Hospital / Government Medical College, Srikakulam, AP. Patients who fulfilled the following criteria were selected.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Maternal age 18-44 years.
2. Patients with single intrauterine pregnancy with cephalic presentation.
3. Patient very sure of her last menstrual period.
4. Previous regular menstrual cycle.

5. No history of using hormonal contraceptive methods six months prior to conception.
6. Confirmation of gestational age and expected date of date by first trimester or early second trimester scanning.

All patients expected date of delivery was calculated as per Naegles formula. Only those patients in which the EDD by LMP and EDD by ultrasonography were coinciding within one week were taken. The patients who were registered and was on regular follow-up had on non-stress test, ultrasound for AFI the time of admission (or within 3 days from the time of admission) and BPP if needed.

Criteria for Induction

Patient who did not go into spontaneous labor even after completion of 42 weeks oligohydramnious, poor biophysical profile. Non-stress test was done on admission for almost all the patients. As per requirement artificial rupture of membrane and augmentation of labor was done with oxytocin drip and smooth muscle relaxation (Drotaverine, Valethamate).

Exclusion: The patients with unknown dates, irregular menstrual period malpresentation, maternal complication like PIH, diabetes and APH were excluded.

Management Protocol on Admission

All those patients who were admitted were assessed on admission and admission test done. The IV line was secured in all patients and hydration was maintained by IV lines or liquids orally.

Proctolysis enema was given to most of patients on admission. Patients who were admitted for induction were induced with prostaglandin E2

(cerviprime) gel intracervically or prostaglandin E1 tablet intravaginally after taking written and informed consent. Patient who were admitted with spontaneous labour were monitored for fetal heart rate, artificial rupture of membranes was done in active phase of labor. Patients with meconium stained liquor were monitored for fetal heart rate with continuous fetal heart rate monitor.

If required labor was augmented with oxytocin. Also drotaverine and valethamate injection were given if required. Patients with indication for caesarian section were prepared preoperatively and written and informed consent taken. The follow-up of the mother was done in the following lines.

- Induction / Spontaneous Labor
- Mode of delivery
 - Vaginal delivery
 - LSCS
 - Instrumental delivery
- Duration of Labor
- Colour of the liquor

The follow-up of the babies were done in the follow lines.

- Apgar Score
- 1 Min and 5 Min
- Weight
- Sex
- Sign of meconium aspiration
- Sign of birth asphyxia
- NICU admission
- Sign of hypoxic ischaemic encephalopathy
- Perinatal Mortality
- Evidence of birth trauma

Observations

Table 1: Age wise distribution of cases and control group

Age	37-40 Weeks	Mean+/-SD	>40 Wks	Mean+/-SD	Significance
<20	21	19.2+/-0.944	25	19.4+/-0.81	T=0.769, P>0.05
21-25	54	23.35+/-1.615	59	23.05+/-1.513	T=1.016, P>0.05
26-30	25	28.04+/-1.567	16	27.625+/-1.63	T=0.94, P>0.05
>30	0		0		

Table 2: Parity wise distribution of cases and control group

Gestational age	Primi	Multi	Total
37-40weeks	53	47	100
>40weeks	68	32	100

Table 3: Type of Labour

Type of labour	37-40 weeks	>40weeks
Spontaneous	100	90
Induced	00	10

Table 4: Mode of Delivery in Cases and Control Group

Mode of Delivery	37-40weeks	>40weeks
Normal vaginal delivery	80	66
Instrumental[forceps]	10	12
LSCS	10	22

Table 5: Type of Delivery by type of labor

Type of Labour	Type of delivery					
	NVD		Instrumental		Caesarean	
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent
Spontaneous	59	65.5	12	13.3	19	21.11
Induced	7	70	--	--	3	30.0
Total	66	66	12	12	22	22.00

$$\chi^2 = 0.46 \text{ p} > 0.05$$

Table 6: Gestational week wise outcome of labor in postdates

No of week of pregnancy	Total no of cases	NVD		LSCS		Instrumental	
		Number	Present	Number	Present	Number	Present
40-41	48	34	70.90	8	16.6	6	12.5
41-42	33	23	69.7	8	24.24	2	6.06
42-43	10	5	50.0	3	30.0	2	20.0
>43	9	4	44.44	3	33.33	2	22.22

Table 7: Comparison of incidence of meconium stained liquor, MAS and HIE in pregnancies beyond 40 weeks and 37-40 weeks

	37-40 weeks		>40 weeks		χ^2
	Number	Present	Number	Present	
Meconium stained liquor	17	17.00	31	31.00	5.3, P<0.01
Meconium aspirated syndrome	02	2.00	09	9.00	
Hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy	01	1.00	02	2.00	

Table 8: Gestational week wise incidence of meconium in pregnancies beyond 40 weeks

Gestational week	Number of cases with meconium stained fluid	percentage
40-41	14	29.1
41-42	10	30.30
Beyond 42 weeks	7	36.8

Table 9: Gestational week wise incidence of meconium in pregnancies between 37-40weeks

Gestational week	No. of cases of meconium stained fluid	Percentage
37-38	5	11.62
38-39	7	17.94
39-40	5	27.7

Table 10: Gestational week wise incidence of meconium aspiration syndrome in post-dates

Gestational Age	Total No. of cases	No. of MAS	Percentage
40-41	48	3	6.25
41-42	33	2	6.06
42-43	10	2	20.0
>43	9	2	22.22

Table 11: Comparison of Incidence of No. of NICU Admission between 37-40 weeks and beyond 40 weeks

Gestational Age	No. of cases	Percentage
37-40	5	5.00
>40weeksweeks	13	13.00

Table 12: Relationship of weeks of gestation to NICU admission beyond 40 weeks

Gestational weeks	No. cases	No. of NICU admission	Percentage
40-41	48	3	6.16
41-42	33	5	5.15
42-43	10	2	20.00
>43	9	3	33.30

Table 13: Number of NICU Admission between 37-40 Weeks

Gestational Age in Weeks	No. of babies admitted in NICU	Percentage
37-38	1	2.30
38-39	3	7.68
39-40	1	5.50

Table 14: Perinatal Mortality

Gestational Age	Still birth	Neonatal death	Total
37-40	0	0	0
>40	1	1	2

Table 15: Parity and Perinatal Mortality

Parity	Perinatal mortality	Percentage
Primi	2	2.00
Multi	0	00

Table 16: Comparison of Incidence of Oligohydramnios between 37-40 weeks and beyond 40 Weeks

Weeks of gestation	No. of cases	Percentage
37-40weeks	2	2.00
>40weeks	9	9.00

Table 17: Fetal Distress

Gestational Age	No. of cases	Percentage
37-40weeks	13	13.00
>40weeks	26	26.00

Fetal distress was diagnosed by the presence of the any one of the following persistent tachycardia or bradycardia, loss of beat to beat variability, severe variable or late deceleration or passage of thick meconium.

Results

During this period women who delivered between 37-40 weeks and those who delivered beyond 40 weeks as determined by early pregnancy dating including accurate last menstrual period, per vaginal examination, first or 2nd trimester ultrasound examination were taken as study and control group respectively.

There were total 100 cases in the study group and 100 cases in the control group. After analyzing the study we group found that 48 (48%) lies in the group of post-datism up to 7 days, 33 (33%) of cases in the group of 8 to 14 days and 19 cases (19%) beyond 14 days postdate.

In this study out of 100 patients 46 patients (46%) went into spontaneous labor during 41st weeks, 29 (29%) went in spontaneous labor during 42nd week and 15 patients (15%) beyond 42nd weeks.

The induction rate in this study was 10%, which is much less than the rate of spontaneous labor (90%). Of the 10 patients induced all were primigravidae

Out of the 10 cases of induction of labour 2 (20%) cases were induced at 41 week for oligohydramnios and 8 (80%) cases induction was done at or beyond 42nd week. Out of the 10 cases, 3 patients underwent caesarian section, 1 for the failed induction and 2 for the fetal distress and 7 delivered normally and no patient had instrumental delivery.

The caesarian section rate in induced labor is 30% compared to caesarean section rate of (21.11%) (19) In the spontaneous group indicating a higher

rate of caesarean section in induced patients. The caesarean section rate at 37-40 weeks is 10% and that of study group is 22%, which is more than double of the control group.

90 patients went into spontaneous labor of which 58 cases were primigravida. 38 (65%) cases delivered normally, 8 (13.79%) cases of instrument delivery of which 3 for prolong II stage and 5 for fetal distress. 12 (20.68%) cases underwent LSCS in which 1 for CPD and 11 for cases for fetal distress.

Among 32 multigravida who went into spontaneous labor, 21 (65.62%) delivered by normal vaginal delivery, 4 (12.5%) by instrumental delivery in which 1 for previous LSCS, 2 for prolong second stage labour and one for fetal distress and 7 (21.87%) delivered by caesarian section in which 6 cases for fetal distress and one case for CPD.

Out of the 100 babies born in study group, there was one intrauterine death due to fetal distress and one baby died in NICU on PND2, 13(13%) babies required NICU admission for birth asphyxia, meconium aspiration or low Apgar score compared to 5 (5%) between 37-40 weeks. There were no perinatal deaths in the control group. In the study group, one baby had cephalohematoma and one baby had shoulder dystocia. With expectant policy, 90% had spontaneous labour. In multiparous women with spontaneous onset of labor, 6 patients underwent LSCS for fetal distress (18.75%) and one for CPD. In primigravida with spontaneous onset of labor caesarian rate for fetal distress is 18.96, which is similar.

Discussion

The perceived risk to the fetus beyond 40 weeks has led to the obstetrician's dilemma of whether to avail spontaneous labor or to artificially bring

forward the onset of labor to an arbitrarily defined gestation. As pregnancy advances to beyond 40 weeks the placental insufficiency sets in because of reduced respiratory and nutritive placenta function.

Age distribution: 59% of pregnancy beyond 40 weeks was between the age group of 21-25 years and 25% were below 20 years of age. A similar observation was made by Eden et al. where the mean age was 25.8 years.

Parity and pregnancy beyond 40 weeks: In the present study pregnancy beyond 40 weeks occurred more frequently in primigravida compared to multigravida. In primigravida the rate was 68% compared to 32% in multigravida. A similar finding was reported by Alexander et al.

Mode of Delivery: The rate of surgical intervention increased in cases of pregnancy beyond 40 weeks because of increased frequency of fetal distress and failed Induction. In the present study, the rate of caesarian section was 22% compared to 10% in the controls.

According to Prabha Singhal et al. the rate of caesarian was 16.7%. In the present study, the rate of 22% is higher probably due to patients being referred to our hospital after a trial of labor being given outside.

Labor Induction Versus Spontaneous: In the present study 10 cases were induced compared to 90 cases, which had spontaneous labor. 30% of induced cases have LSCS and in the spontaneous group, the LSCS rate is 21.11%. The rate of caesarian section beyond 41 weeks in spontaneous group is 27.27%. Caesarian section rate of 21.1% was reported by Kaplan et al. Our study is comparable with it.

Forceps Delivery: The present study shows an incidence of 12% of forceps delivery compared to 10% in the control. Alexander et al. had 8% at 41 weeks and 9% of instrumental delivery at 42 weeks.

Neonatal Morbidity: In the present study meconium stained liquor was found in 31% of cases compared to 17% of cases in control group. The incidence of meconium stained is 36.36% (spontaneous group) in the present study. The risk of meconium aspiration syndrome is 9% beyond 40 weeks i.e., 6.06 beyond 41 weeks and 21.11% beyond 42 weeks.

Birth Weight: The mean birth weight in the study group is 3.065 Kg and control group is 2.49 Kg.

Perinatal Mortality and Sex of the Baby: The overall perinatal mortality in our study group is 2% (2 cases) and both of which are male and both were beyond 42 weeks.

The perinatal mortality at >42 weeks is 1 case (10%) and beyond 43 weeks 1 case (11.11%).

Perinatal Mortality beyond 40 weeks and 37-40 week: The perinatal mortality is 2% in the study group compared to 0% in the control group. This can be reduced by early referral and early intervention in termination of pregnancy.

Oligohydramnios: There is 9% incidence of oligohydramnios in the study group compared to 2% in the control group i.e., AFI<5 cm).

Hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (post asphyxia encephalopathy): There was 2% incidence of HIE in study group out of which 1 baby died on PND2. In the control group, the incidence is 1%. One case was beyond 41 weeks (2.08%) and 1 was beyond 42 weeks (5.2%). There were 2 (2%) babies which were macrosomic of which one delivered vaginally had shoulder dystocia and birth asphyxia and one delivered by caesarean. There was one case of cephalohematoma in the study group.

Fetal Distress: In our study, the incidence of fetal distress is 26% compared to 13% in the control group.

We selected the patients for induction who did not go in spontaneous labor even after completion of 42nd week or patients with oligohydramnios, abnormal NST or biophysical profile when the cervix was favourable. Immediate termination of pregnancy was done when there was evidence of fetal distress or CPD. So till the fetal surveillance tests are normal induction is not necessary till 42 weeks as our 90% patients had gone in spontaneous labor. Among them 48% of cases went into spontaneous labor by first week of post expected date of delivery, 33% went in 2nd week and 10% went in 3rd week. We found that the caesarian section rate in induced group (30%) is higher than the spontaneous group. The outcome of labor in spontaneous group (mode of delivery) with respect to induced group was not statistically significant different $p>0.005$.

We found that caesarian section rate in primigravida in spontaneous group is less than that of induced group (20.6 vs 30%) out of the 85.2% of primigravida who went into spontaneous labour 20.6% required caesarean section. The main indication being fetal distress. The overall caesarian section rate in primigravida is 22% and that of multigravida is (21.87%), which is almost same.

NICU Admission: The NICU admission in our study group is 13% compared to 5% in the control group, which was statistically significant. On further analysis, we found that as the gestational weeks increased, the rate of NICU admission increased i.e., at 40 – 41 weeks it is 6.16% at 41-42

weeks it is 15.15% and at more than 42 weeks it is 24.31%.

Gross Asphyxia: In our study the incidence of gross asphyxia is 3.03% at 41-42, 10% beyond 42 weeks and 22.2% beyond 43 weeks.

Conclusion

The management of pregnancy beyond 40 weeks remains controversial. The value of routine induction of labour in such pregnancy also remains controversial because of the concern that it may result in an increase in the incidence of caesarean section without any significant improvement in the fetal outcome. In infants admitted to NICU one of the risk factor attributed is post datism. So care of the post-dated fetus should start right from in utero. In this complex clinical condition, we should identify the fetus at risk and to institute an appropriate management following adequate counselling of patient.

This study shows a 2-fold increase in meconium release and 4-fold increase in frequency of meconium aspiration compared to control group. There is also concomitant increase in the birth asphyxia and depression at birth requiring ventilation. The perinatal mortality is increase 2% compared to the control group (0%). Fetal distress and meconium stain liquor when present have ominous significance but their absence is much more reassuring. The presence of meconium stained liquor should alert the obstetrician. Appropriate steps like suctioning of pharynx should be done as soon as head is delivered. We suggest that with a very high accuracy of gestational age all patients post EDD should be followed regularly with strict antenatal fetal surveillance. These patients should be induced at the earliest sign of any type of fetal compromise irrespective of Bishop score.

The fact that the intensive care necessary admission increases is concerning both for the neonatal morbidity and mortality but also for the use of medical resources and cost even though there are no perinatal death before 42 weeks of gestation, the perinatal morbidity is increased. The lowest being at 37 completed weeks. In view of low neonatal intensive care unit admission it may be wiser to deliver the patient before 40 weeks.

References

1. Ballantyne JW. The problem of postmature infant. *J. Obstet Gynecol. Br. Emp.* 1902; 2: 36.
2. Frank C, Miller MD, John A Read. Lieutenant Commander, MC, USA. Intrapartum assessment of the post-date fetus. *Am. J. Obstetrics & Gynaecol.* 1981; 141: 516.
3. Cunningham FG, Kenneth J Leveno, Steven L Bloom, John C Hauth, Larry Gilstrap III, Katharine D, Weinstrom, Prolong pregnancy, Williams Obstetric, 22nd Edition, USA, McGraw Hill. 2005; 882-892.
4. Fernando Arias. Practical guide to high risk pregnancy & delivery 2 Edition; India (Reprint) Harcourt private limited, 1993; 150-161.
5. Hacker & Moore. Essential of obstetrics & Gynecology, 3rd Edition, 1998; 328-329.
6. Beisher et al. Incidence of prolonged pregnancy. *Am Journal of Gynecology*, 1968; 103: 476.
7. Mclure Brown JC. Postmaturity. *Am. J. Obstetrics & Gyanael*, 1963; 85: 473.
8. Roberts LJ, Young KR. The management of prolonged pregnancy – an analysis of women's attitude before and after-term. *Br. J. of Obstet & Gynecology* 1991; 98: 1102-1106.
9. Clifford SH. Postmaturity with placental dysfunction. *J. of Pediatrics.* 1954; 44: 1.
10. Kloosterman GJ. Prolonged pregnancy. 1956.